

Lesson Reinforcement Skills of Teachers: Basis for Study Habit Development Among Grade Six Learners

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Abstract. This study sought to determine the level of lesson reinforcement skills of teachers, which served as the basis for designing a study habit development program for learners. The study employed a non-experimental descriptive survey research design to investigate the research problem. It was descriptive because the data were presented through quantitative descriptions of the 'Lesson Reinforcement Skills of Teachers: Basis for Study Habit Development Program.' According to Good (2005), this method of research merely described tasks by presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events involved in the procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involved varied information regarding the current or present condition. This study took place in elementary schools within the Sta. Cruz North district. The respondents in this study were 50 elementary school teachers from the research locale. The respondents' lesson reinforcement skills were evaluated using a classroom observation tool by their school heads. The researcher wrote a letter to the concerned school heads to obtain the above-mentioned data. This study revealed that the reinforcement skills of teachers were important in the teaching-learning situation. If reinforcement was very intensive, then academic outcomes among students were also high.

KEY WORDS

1. reinforcement. 2. study habit.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the landscape of education has been increasingly shaped by the integration of technology and the challenges posed by events like the COVID-19 pandemic. These factors have underscored the urgent need for innovative approaches in educational practices, emphasizing the shift towards blended and remote learning environments (Borero, 2021). Understanding and enhancing teachers' ability to reinforce lessons effectively is crucial in this evolving context. Effective lesson reinforcement helps students consolidate their learning, retain information better, and apply knowledge. Therefore, equipping teachers with robust reinforcement skills is essential for fostering an environment where students are motivated to engage deeply with the material. This study seeks to pinpoint the strengths and gaps in current teaching practices at Almendras Elementary School, aiming to bolster these skills and, consequently, improve student outcomes. Study habits are pivotal in shaping students' academic success, influencing their ability to manage time, set goals, and engage effectively with course ma-

materials (Pichitte, 2010). According to Gopalakrishnan (2017), the development of good study habits significantly impacts academic achievements, underscoring the importance of addressing this aspect in educational settings. Effective study habits include strategies such as organizing study time, using active learning techniques, and maintaining a conducive study environment. Yet, challenges persist, as identified by Mark and Howard (2009), who emphasize the detrimental effects of poor study habits on student performance across various academic levels. These challenges include procrastination, lack of motivation, and inadequate study strategies, which can hinder students' ability to perform well in assessments and exams. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach that includes not only enhancing students' study skills but also providing teachers with the tools and strategies to support and reinforce these habits effectively. In the specific context of Almendras Elementary School, located in the Sta. Cruz North district of the Division of Davao Del Sur, concerns about study habits among learners have been pronounced (MacKay, 2021). Despite efforts by teachers to reinforce lessons, retention among students remains a persistent issue, prompting the need for focused investigation and intervention (Cooper, 2016). Observations and assessments at the school indicate that many students struggle to retain information and apply what they have learned in new contexts. This lack of retention is a critical concern, as it affects students' ability to build on their knowledge and succeed in more advanced levels of education. The study aims to delve into the root causes of these issues, exploring how teachers' reinforcement strategies may be enhanced to improve students' study habits and overall academic performance. By identifying specific areas where intervention is needed, the study hopes to contribute to the development of targeted programs that can effectively address these challenges. The literature review

underscores various methodologies and insights pertinent to the study's objectives. For instance, the use of drill and practice, characterized by systematic repetition, has been advocated as a method to enhance learning outcomes (Cheung Leung-Ngai, 2020). This method helps in reinforcing knowledge through repetitive practice, ensuring that students retain and can recall information effectively. Similarly, contextualization of lessons within real-world scenarios has been shown to improve engagement and comprehension among students (Martínez, 2020). When students see the relevance of what they are learning to their everyday lives or future careers, they are more likely to be motivated and engaged. This approach bridges the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application, making learning more meaningful and impactful. The review also highlights the importance of varied instructional strategies, including collaborative learning, problem-solving tasks, and the integration of technology, to enhance the effectiveness of lesson reinforcement. Effective monitoring and evaluation of student performance further contribute to educational success (Odinko, 2021). This practice not only helps in identifying areas needing improvement but also informs instructional strategies tailored to students' specific needs (Tandberg, 2020). By systematically collecting and analyzing data on student performance, teachers can make informed decisions about their teaching methods and interventions. Such insights are critical in shaping the theoretical and conceptual framework of this study, which draws on Hallam's (2012) theory emphasizing the role of home learning environments in fostering study habits. Hallam's theory suggests that structured and supportive home learning environments can significantly enhance students' study habits and academic performance. This study will explore how teachers can create such environments through effective lesson reinforcement and how these practices can be supported by parental involvement and commu-

nity resources. The theoretical framework also integrates perspectives on teacher scaffolding and parental involvement, which are pivotal in guiding effective home learning practices (Soo, 2017). These insights will inform the methodological approach of the study, which employs a non-experimental descriptive survey design to assess teachers' reinforcement skills through classroom observations conducted by school heads. Teacher scaffolding involves providing appropriate support and guidance to students, helping them develop the skills they need to learn independently. Parental involvement, on the other hand, includes activities that encourage parents to engage with their children's education, such as helping with homework or participating in school events. By combining these elements, the study aims to develop a comprehensive understanding of how teachers can effectively reinforce lessons and support students' study habits both in and out of the classroom. In conclusion, this introduction sets the stage for a comprehensive exploration into the reinforcement skills of teachers at Almendras Elementary School and their impact on students' study habits. By addressing these aspects, the study aims to contribute valuable insights into educational practices that can enhance learning outcomes and inform the development of targeted interventions. This research is guided by the principles of clarity, logical flow, and integration of relevant literature, ensuring a robust foundation for addressing the identified research gaps and achieving the study's objectives (Hardy, Lawrence, 2016). The findings from this study are expected to provide actionable recommendations for educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to enhance the effectiveness of teaching practices and improve students' academic performance. Through a thorough investigation of lesson reinforcement skills and their impact on study habits, the study aims to pave the way for innovative strategies and programs that can significantly enhance educational out-

comes at Almendras Elementary School and beyond.

The key to becoming an effective student is learning how to study smarter, not harder. This becomes more and truer as you advance in your education. An hour or two of studying a day is usually sufficient to make it through high school with satisfactory grades, but when college arrives, there are not enough hours in the day to get all your studying in if you do not know how to study smarter. Successful students schedule specific times throughout the week when they are going to study – and then they stick with their schedule. Students who study sporadically and whimsically typically do not perform as well as students who have a set study schedule. Even if you are all caught up with your studies, creating a weekly routine, where you set aside a period a few days a week, to review your courses will ensure you develop habits that will enable you to succeed in your education long term. Study habits reflect students' usual act of studying and call forth and serve to direct the learner's cognitive processes during learning. Study habits includes a variety of activities: time management, setting appropriate goals, choosing an appropriate study environment, using appropriate note-taking strategies, choosing main ideas, and organization (Proctor et al., 2006). Fielden (20014) states that good study habits help the student in critical reflection in skills outcomes such as selecting, analyzing, critiquing, and synthesizing. Study habits are learning tendencies that enable students work privately. Azikiwe (1998) describes study habits as the way and manner a student plans his or her private reading outside lecture hours to master a particular subject or topic. Study habits help students master their areas of specialization. Study habit is one of the greatest students or learning factors that hugely influences students' academic achievements. If undermined by students at all levels, teachers, administrators, parents and guardians, school counselors

and the government, then, the trend and menace of students' abysmal performance in both internal and external examinations would continue to boom and become more devastating and alarming. Mark and Howard (2009) are of the opinion that the most common challenge to the success of students in all ramifications is a lack of effective or positive (good) study habit. They further maintain that if students can develop a good study habit and with good discipline, they are bound to perform remarkably well in their academic pursuit. In the Division of Davao Del Sur particularly in Almendras Elementary School, Sta. Cruz North district, problem in study habit among learners is prevalent. Teachers may do reinforcement of the lesson, but the learners tend to forget the lesson the day after. Poor study is a prevailing problem in school. Hence this study.

1.1. Review of Significant Literature—

1.1.1. *Study Habits*—Effective study habits are essential for academic success. Key components include smart study techniques, consistent scheduling, and appropriate study environments (Bremer, 2015; Shankman, 2016). Good study habits help in critical reflection and mastering subjects (Cohn, 2017; Gruber, 2016). Effective study habits can combat poor academic performance (Gopalakrishnan, 2017) and are crucial for long-term academic success (Werner, 2017; Carey, 2015; Reynolds, 2016). Establishing good study habits early in life is vital, and these habits significantly impact academic outcomes (Hourcade, 2017; Galloway, 2018; Cooper, 2016; Wood, 2016). Parents and teachers play a critical role in developing these habits (Ystgaard, 2017; Rah, 2017; Hardy, 2016).

1.1.2. *Lesson Reinforcement*—Positive reinforcement encourages desired behaviors by providing incentives immediately after achievements (Revermann, 2021). Effective reinforcement should be timely, genuine, and appropriate for the student's age (Revermann, n.d.).

1.1.3. *Lesson Drill*—Drills, such as flash-card exercises, enhance learning by promoting repetition and practice (Bempechat, 2015). This method improves accuracy and fluency, providing a safe environment for students to practice language and receive immediate feedback (Cheung Leung-Ngai, 2020; Pope, 2016; Richards, 2020; Liebman, 2017).

1.1.4. *Contextualization*—Contextualizing lessons by linking new information to real-life situations and prior knowledge enhances understanding and retention (Pichitte, 2010; Hussain, 2022). This approach makes learning more relevant and engaging across various subjects, including history, science, literature, and mathematics (Borero, 2021; Martínez, 2020; MacKay, 2021).

1.1.5. *Monitoring and Evaluation of Students' Performance*—Evaluating student performance helps inform instructional decisions and improve educational programs (Odinko, 2021). Effective monitoring involves setting targets and assessing progress to ensure resources are utilized effectively (Kaufman, 2020). Quality assurance in education can be achieved through various models and is critical for maintaining high educational standards (Cheng, 2001; Tandberg, 2020).

1.2. *Synthesis*—The above-stated review of significant literatures discussed the prevalence of the problem under study in different context. They also discussed methodologies on how the current issue is solved. There are findings and recommendations presented to resolve the problem. These literatures backed up the occurrence of the problem and different localities present solutions. They also serve as roadmap to guide the researcher in the conduct of the study.

1.3. *Theoretical/Conceptual Framework*—This study is anchored on the theory of Hallam (2012) who said that Home learning is proven to be more effective with older students than their younger counterparts. This is typically because

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

they are more able to self-regulate their learning and they have more background knowledge to draw upon. For similar reasons, high ability students typically benefit more from home learning than low ability students. Frequent home learning may result to establishment of good study habit. This is supported by Soo (2017) who expressed that teacher scaffolding is essential to guide effective home learning. Parental involvement is desirable, but it should not be essential, otherwise the nature of the task is too complex for successful completion. When

teacher gives homework to learners and regularly checks them, then, the learners can form good study habit. The diagram that follows illustrates the flow of the study. The skills of teachers in lesson reinforcement will be the focus of this study. Classroom observation results are very helpful to the researcher to determine the reinforcement skills of the teachers. Eventually, this study will measure the study habit skills of the learners as the effect of the reinforcement skills of the learners.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—This study seeks to determine the level of the lesson reinforcement skills of teachers which will be the

basis in designing a study habit development program for learners. Specifically, it seeks answers to the following sub-problems:

- (1) 1. What is the level of the lesson reinforcement skills of the teachers in terms of:
 - (1) Lesson Drill
 - (2) Contextualization
 - (3) Monitoring and Evaluation?
- (2) Based on the findings of this study, what study development skills program can be designed and developed?

1.5. Hypothesis—Since this study does not seek for relationship nor difference between and among variables, this study is hypothesis-free.

1.6. Significance of the Study—The following are considered beneficiaries of the study. DepEd Officials. This research will provide the foundation for DepEd Officials to organize a range of seminars and pertinent training programs for teachers in the early grades, particularly in teaching strategy. This is an effective way to address pedagogical problems among teachers as this will give idea to teachers on

what strategy will be used when teaching a particular lesson. School Administrators. The findings of this study are beneficial to the school head to design a school-based training for teachers that would address their problem in teaching pedagogy that would suit to the learning styles of their learners. Teachers. The findings of this research study are helpful to all teachers in the basic Education curriculum because all teachers across subject areas need to have pool of strategies where they can choose from during their daily classroom instruction activities. Future Researchers. The findings of this study may en-

courage them to conduct similar studies in other areas. This study serves as an additional source of reference and inquiries for their investigation relative to the present study.

1.7. *Definition of Terms*—To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are operationally and conceptually defined. Lesson Reinforcement Skills refers to the ability of the ability of the teachers to present lesson simi-

lar his current lesson to make follow up of the students learning. According to Smith (2017), reinforcement refers to “a stimulus which follows and is contingent upon a behavior and increases the probability of a behavior being repeated”. The simplest way of conceptualizing positive reinforcement is that something pleasant is ‘added’ when a specific action is performed (Cherry, 2018).

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. *Research Locale and Sample*—This study was conducted in the elementary schools in Sta. Cruz North District. The respondents in this study are the 50 elementary school teachers of the research locale. The respondents’ lesson

reinforcement skills will be assessed through the classroom observation tool from the position of their school heads. The researcher will write a letter to the school heads concern so that the above-mentioned data will be given to her.

Distribution of Respondents

Schools	No. of Teachers
Almendras Elementary School	19
Marcos P. Saez Elementary School	21
Astorga Central Elementary School	10
TOTAL	50

2.2. *Data Source and Analysis*—This study employed the non-experimental descriptive survey research design in investigating the research problem. It is descriptive because the data are presented in quantitative descriptions on the “lesson Reinforcement Skills of Teachers: Basis for study habit development program. According to Good (2005), this method of research shows merely description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding

the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005). The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the level of the lesson reinforcement skills of the teachers.

This study was utilized the hard data on the classroom observation in the possession of the school heads. The researcher able to retrieve the data from the school heads or master teachers through a written request. Since the tool used is standardized, there is no need for pilot testing to measure its validity and reliability. To deter-

mine the level of the lesson reinforcement skills used. of the teachers, the following continuum will be

Scale	Level	Criteria
5	Very High	When the provisions on lesson reinforcement skills of teachers are manifested all the time.
4	High	When the provisions on lesson reinforcement skills of teachers are frequently manifested.
3	Moderate	When the provisions on lesson reinforcement skills of teachers are sometimes manifested.
2	Low	When the provisions on lesson reinforcement skills of teachers are seldom manifested.
1	Very Low	When the provisions on lesson reinforcement skills of teachers are never manifested.

2.3. *Data Gathering and Processing*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft letter signed by the Dean of the Graduate School seeking for permission that this research study be conducted and will be sent to the office of the Schools Division Superintendent in the Division of Davao Del Sur and to the School Principals of Sta. Cruz North District elementary schools. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepEd Schools Division Superintendent and principal concerned, the researcher constructed

a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in the elementary schools of Sta. Cruz North district and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will launch the questionnaire to the respondent. Responses of the respondents will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Level of Lesson Reinforcement Skills in terms of lesson drill, Level of Lesson Reinforcement Skills in terms of contextualization of the lesson, Level of Lesson Reinforcement Skills in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation, and Significant relationship between Lesson Reinforcement skills of teachers and Study Habit Development Among Grade Six Learners.

3.1. *Level Reinforcement Skills in terms of Lesson Drill*—Table 1 shows the level of lesson reinforcement skills in terms of lesson drill. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Identifies least learned lesson with a rating of 4.38 or very high, Includes drill in the recent lesson with a rating of 4.36 or

very high, Continues the conduct of the drill with a rating of 4.35 or very high, Applies effective drill strategy with a rating of 4.10 or high, and Assesses the proficiency level of the learners with a rating of 4.07 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.25 or high. This means that teachers always conduct review of the lesson that are not mastered by the learn-

ers through drill. Cheung Leung-Ngai (2020) provides evidence for this viewpoint. The term drill and practice are defined as a method of instruction characterized by systematic repetition of concepts, examples, and practice problems. Drill and practice are a disciplined and repetitious exercise, used as a mean of teaching and perfecting a skill or procedure. As an instructional strategy, it promotes the acquisition of knowledge or skill through systematic training by multiple repetitions, rehearse, practice, and engages in a rehearsal to learn or become proficient. Like memorization, drill and practice involves repetition of specific skills, such as spelling or multiplication. To develop or maintain one’s specific skills, the subskills built through drill and practice should become the building blocks for more meaningful learning. Lesson drill is a popular teaching technique that has been demonstrated to be successful in rais-

ing academic achievement across a range of topics and grade levels, which lends credence to Hattie’s (2022) assertion. However, elements include the sort of content being drilled, the spacing and scheduling of practice sessions, and individual student characteristics may have an impact on how successful lesson drills are. In addition, drill provides for a focus on accuracy. Increased accuracy (along with increased fluency and complexity) is one of the ways in which a learner’s language improves so there is a need to focus on accuracy at certain stages of the lesson or during certain task types. Moreover, it provides learners with intensive practice in hearing and saying particular words or phrases. They can help learners get their tongues around difficult sounds or help them imitate intonation that may be different from that of their first language (Richards, 2020).

Table 1: Level Reinforcement Skills in terms of Lesson Drill

Reinforcement Skills	Mean	Description
a. Identifies least learned lesson	4.38	Very High
b. Applies effective drill strategy	4.10	High
c. Includes drill in the recent lesson	4.36	Very High
d. Assesses the proficiency level of the learners	4.07	High
e. Continues the conduct of the drill	4.35	Very High
Overall	4.25	High

3.2. *Level Reinforcement Skills in terms of Contextualization of the Lesson*—Table 2 presents the level of lesson reinforcement skills in terms of contextualization of the lesson. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Relates lesson to the context of the learners with a rating of 4.40 or high, Fits lesson to current situation with a rating of 4.14 or high, Integrates culture of the places

with a rating of 4.27 or high, Unleash meanings based on the prior knowledge of the learners with a rating of 4.19 or high, and Select a teaching strategy that aids the understanding of the learners with a rating of 4.36 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.27 or high. This means that teachers always localized situations in the lesson for more emphasis to the learners. Further, this means that teachers possess good skills in contextualizing lessons to suit to the

understanding of the learners. Renninger (2006) provides support for this approach, noting that research has consistently shown the advantages of contextualization in lesson design. Contextualized training encourages deeper knowledge, increases information retention, and strengthens the transfer of learning to new circumstances by using real-world examples and applications. Furthermore, by making learning more relevant and meaningful, contextualization contributes to an increase in student motivation and engagement. Bransford (2022) argues that contextualizing teachings is an essential part of good lesson design and delivery. Contextualized training encourages deeper comprehension, increases information retention, and boosts student motivation by relating new learning to students' existing knowledge, experiences, and real-world applications. Contextualization in lessons has

numerous benefits for student learning. When students can connect current information to real-life situations or prior knowledge, they are more likely to understand and retain the information. Contextualization helps students see the relevance and practical application of what they are learning, which increases their motivation and engagement. It also promotes critical thinking skills as students are encouraged to analyze and evaluate how the information relates to larger societal issues or challenges. Additionally, contextualization allows for a more personalized learning experience, as students can make personal connections to the content and apply it to their own lives. Overall, incorporating contextualization into lessons enhances student learning and helps them develop a deeper understanding of the material (Hussain, 2022).

Table 2: Level Reinforcement Skills in terms of Contextualization of the Lesson

Reinforcement Skills	Mean	Description
a. Select a teaching strategy that aids the understanding of the learners	4.36	Very High
b. Relates lesson to the context of the learners	4.40	Very High
c. Unleash meanings based on the prior knowledge of the learners	4.19	Very High
d. Fits lesson to current situation	4.14	Very High
e. Integrates culture of the places	4.27	Very High
Overall	4.27	Very High

3.3. *Level Reinforcement Skills in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation*—Table 3 emphasizes the level of lesson reinforcement skills in terms of monitoring and evaluation. In this discussion the following responses yielded by the respondents are given for a comprehensive emphasis: Follows up the daily lesson by giving a similar lesson with a rating of 4.40 or very high, introduces new lesson by giving assignment with a rating of 4.33 or very high, gives

bring home activity to learners with a rating of 4.26 or high, Checks assignment with a rating of 4.06 or high, and Collects assignment with a rating of 4:00 or high. It got an overall mean rating of 4.21 or high. This means that teachers always monitor the academic progress of their learners. They use variety of tools to monitor performances of the learners. This concept aligns with UNICEF's (2019) notion that monitoring entails the methodical gathering and ex-

amination of data to trace advancements and pinpoint opportunities for enhancement, whereas evaluation entails evaluating the efficacy and influence of educational initiatives and interventions. When combined, monitoring and assessment offer insightful data that may be used to improve educational quality, allocate resources, and make decisions. Odinko (2021) opted that the primary purpose of evaluation of student’s learning outcomes in each educational program is to provide information for decision making about the program. It could also be seen as a method of acquiring and processing evidence needed to improve the learning and teaching activities (formative). Monitoring involves setting targets and milestones to measure progress and achievement, and finding out whether the imports are producing the planned outputs, which is monitoring sees whether the project is con-

sistent with the sign. Fullan (2021) provides support for this. Monitoring and assessment are essential for raising the standard of instruction and student learning objectives. ME systems contribute to continuous improvement in education delivery by supplying essential data for decision-making, resource allocation, and quality improvement. They also assist maintain accountability. In today’s education, school success is defined as ensuring achievement for every student. To reach this goal, educators need tools to help them identify students who are at risk academically and adjust instructional strategies to better meet these students’ needs. Student progress monitoring is a practice that helps teachers use student performance data to continually evaluate the effectiveness of their teaching and make more informed instructional decisions (Tandberg, 2020).

Table 3: Summary of Reinforcement Skills Level Reinforcement Skills in terms of Monitoring and Evaluation

Reinforcement Skills	Mean	Description
a. Follows up the daily lesson by giving a similar lesson	4.40	Very High
b. Gives bring home activity to learners	4.26	High
c. Introduces new lesson by giving assignment	4.33	Very High
d. Collects assignment	4.00	High
e. Checks assignment	4.06	High
Overall	4.21	High

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. Findings—This study sought to determine the level of the lesson reinforcement skills of teachers which will be the basis in designing a study habit development program for learners. This study employed the non-experimental descriptive survey research design in investigat-

ing the research problem. The study is descriptive because the researchers present the data in quantitative descriptions on the 'lesson Reinforcement Skills of Teachers: Basis for study habit development program. According to Good (2005), this method of research shows merely

description of tasks presenting the conditions regarding the nature of the group of persons or class of events that involved procedure of analysis, classification, and measurement. It involves varied information regarding the current or present condition (Deauna, 2005). The study will be descriptive because the researchers will conduct it using quantitative descriptions of the 'Lesson Reinforcement Skills of Teachers: Basis for study habit development program. The respondents' lesson reinforcement skills will be assessed by their school heads using the classroom observation tool. The researcher will write a letter to the concerned school heads requesting that they provide her with the above-mentioned data. This study revealed that reinforcement skills of teachers is important in the teaching-learning situation. If reinforcement is very intensive, then academic outcomes among students is also high. Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The lesson reinforcement skills of teachers in terms of drill is High. The lesson reinforcement skills of teachers in terms of contextualization is High. The lesson reinforcement skills of teachers in terms of monitoring and evaluation is High.

*4.2. Limitations and Recommendations—*In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers should conduct reinforcement of the lesson to intensify the absorption of the lesson by the students. Reinforcement also supports learning to happen in our students. One example of the lesson might be not enough to majority of the learners so there is a need for reinforcement to achieve higher academic outcomes. The school heads should have observed very keenly during his/her classroom observation to determine what skills teacher need to master as they unfold the lesson during teaching-learning situations. Reinforcement should be

given more emphasis by the school head because comprehension happens when things are clearer to the learners. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on lesson reinforcement skills of teachers with other variables in classroom instruction will be conducted.

*4.3. Conclusions and Rejections—*The critical role of lesson reinforcement skills among teachers in enhancing educational outcomes is paramount. Including high proficiency in employing drill and practice methodologies, which emphasize systematic repetition, effectively reinforces lesson content and solidifies students' understanding and retention of key concepts. Moreover, focusing on accuracy through drill sessions aids in mastering specific skills essential for language development. With contextualization of lessons, educators excel at relating content to students' real-world contexts and prior knowledge, thereby enhancing engagement and relevance. Contextualized learning not only deepens comprehension but also fosters critical thinking and application skills vital to students' holistic development. Teachers' adeptness in monitoring and evaluating student progress through diverse assessment tools and follow-up activities supports ongoing improvement in teaching practices and student outcomes. These findings highlight the importance of further integrating these effective strategies into teacher training programs and curriculum development to optimize educational experiences. Future research should explore the longitudinal impacts of these practices on student achievement and investigate emerging technologies that can enhance educational monitoring and evaluation systems. By leveraging these insights, educators and policymakers can collaboratively enhance educational quality and student success in evolving educational landscapes.

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